

EXPLORING THE MOTIVATION AND CHALLENGES OF NON-EDUCATION GRADUATES MAKING A CAREER SHIFT TO TEACHING IN PALAVILLA INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the motivations and challenges faced by non-education graduates transitioning to teaching at Palavilla Integrated School, Lutayan II district. It investigates factors driving their career shift, typical transition pathways, encountered challenges, and coping mechanisms. Employing qualitative research via key informant interviews, the study revealed motivations such as a focus on education and empowerment, passion for making a difference, and considerations for financial stability. Non-education graduates prioritize student-centered teaching, seek support and mentorship, and value work-life balance, viewing teaching as a path to personal fulfillment and job security. The pathways facilitated successful transitions, addressing factors like job stability, flexibility, and professional development. Despite challenges such as burnout, credibility issues, and mental health concerns, non-education graduates employed strategies like ongoing professional development, determination, and collaboration to succeed. Recommendations included understanding diverse motivations, providing support for transitions, and prioritizing mental health initiatives to enrich the teaching workforce and enhance educator success. Educational institutions were urged to foster a positive environment, embracing professional growth, collaboration, and adaptability while ensuring access to learning resources. Overall, by being proactive and seeking support, non-education graduates can thrive in their new teaching careers, positively impacting students' lives and enriching the field of education.

Keywords: *motivations, challenges, transitions, and support.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing trend of individuals with non-educational backgrounds seeking to make a significant career shift into the field of teaching. This phenomenon raises intriguing questions about the motivations driving these career transitions, as well as the unique challenges faced by these non-traditional educators in their pursuit of teaching career.

According to Goodwin, A., & Kosnik, C. (2013), becoming a teacher educator involves more than a job title. One becomes a teacher educator as soon as one does teacher education, but one's professional identity as a teacher educator is constructed over time. Developing an identity and practices in teacher education is best understood as a process of becoming. Though the work of teaching shares much in common with the work of teacher education, the two positions are significantly divergent in important ways.

In 2018, 16.4% of Filipino workers stated during the Labor Force Survey (LFS) period that they wanted to have more work hours in their present jobs, or to have an additional job, or to have a new job with longer work hours, i.e., declared themselves underemployed (Felipe, J., Sawada, Y., Estrada, G., & Bajaro, D. 2019). The pressing problem of unemployment and underemployment in the Philippines is viewed to be a product of job mismatch which in turn is a result of the diffusion of the interest in academic disciplines in the country. This interest has become the input to the work force of the Philippine industries (Quimilat, M. 2021).

In Lutayan District II, particularly in Palavilla Integrated School, there were some identified teachers employed who render their services in the field of education even though they're not education graduates. The researcher desires to conduct a study on Exploring the Motivation and Challenges of Non-Education Graduates Making a Career Shift to Teaching in Palavilla Integrated School, Lutayan II district.

Additionally, within the context of the Philippines, particularly at Palavilla Integrated School in the Lutayan II district, there has been a notable absence of research investigating the motivations and challenges encountered by non-education graduates who choose to shift their careers to teaching. Previous research in this setting has predominantly concentrated on assessing teachers' performance and the strategies employed in the classroom, irrespective of their educational backgrounds. This study addresses a significant gap in the current literature by homing in on the experiences of non-education graduates transitioning to the teaching profession. While extensive research exists on conventional teacher education routes, there is a dearth of information regarding the motivations and challenges faced by individuals with diverse educational backgrounds entering the teaching field.

Research Questions

This study focused on Exploring the Motivation and Challenges of Non-Education Graduates Making a Career Shift to Teaching at Palavilla Integrated School.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the factors or experiences motivating non-education graduates to consider a career in teaching?
2. What pathways do non-education graduates typically follow when transitioning into a teaching career?
3. What are the challenges and problems encountered by non-education graduates in career shifts into the teaching profession?
4. How do non-education graduates cope with the challenges and problems encountered in transitioning into a teaching career shift?

METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research design employed in the study aimed to delve into the motivation and challenges encountered by non-education graduates transitioning to a teaching career at Palavilla Integrated School in Lutayan District II, Lutayan, Sultan Kudarat. This approach allowed researcher to gather rich, detailed insights into the experiences of individuals making this career shift, providing valuable context, and understanding of their motivations and challenges.

The study focused on the participation of five (5) non-education graduates employed in Palavilla Integrated School. The identified non-education graduates are considered as informants of the Key Informant Interview. It was conducted for the school year 2023-2024.

RESULTS

Factors or experiences motivating non-education graduates to consider a career in teaching the themes that were generated were Educational Focus and Empowerment, Self-care and Professional Growth, and Financial Stability Considerations.

On the Pathways non-education graduates typically follow transitioning into a teaching career the following themes were generated Career Shift, Career Transition Programs, Streamlined Pathway for Certification, and Efficiency of Alternative Pathways

On Challenges and problems encountered by non-education graduates in career shift into the teaching profession, Professional and Career Challenges, Lack of Support, Formal Training and Seminars, Mental Health, and Well-being Issues.

As non-education graduates cope with the challenges and problems encountered in transitioning into a career shift, the following themes were generated, Professional

DISCUSSION

Factors or experiences motivating non-education graduates to consider a career in teaching

1. Educational Focus and Empowerment

Educational focus and empowerment are interconnected concepts that are essential for personal and societal development. Educational focus refers to the concentration and direction of efforts and resources towards specific learning goals and outcomes. It involves prioritizing certain knowledge, skills, and values within the educational system to meet the needs of individuals and society.

Educational Focus and empowerment comprise two different areas student-centered teaching and educator's perspective and motivation.

Student-centered Teaching. It is an approach to education that prioritizes the needs, interests, and abilities of students, placing them at the center of the learning process. Unlike traditional teacher-centered methods, where the instructor delivers information and directs the learning experience, student-centered teaching empowers learners to take an active role in their education.

To support this idea here are the statement responses of the informants.

"In the teaching profession, we aim to teach students to excel in almost all aspects of their lives so that eventually, they will become productive members of society."

"The sense of satisfaction that comes from helping students succeed academically, socially, and emotionally can be deeply rewarding for me."

"I find fulfillment in the relationships I build with my students, the sense of accomplishment that comes from helping them succeed, and the satisfaction of seeing the impact over time."

The student-centered approach has been the center of attention in teaching and learning as the emphasis to shift away from the teacher-centered approach is growing. While the term has been widely used, it remains unclear how it can be effectively operationalized given the continuum nature of teacher-centered and student-centered approaches (Tang, K. 2014).

Educator's Perspective and Motivation. When educators are motivated and maintain a positive perspective, they are more likely to inspire and empower their students, foster a love for learning, and achieve meaningful educational outcomes. Therefore, supporting educators in cultivating a positive perspective and fostering their motivation is essential for promoting excellence in teaching and enhancing student success. The informants said the following statement;

“Passion for a subject or field, coupled with a desire to make a difference, can drive individuals towards career change and personal fulfillment, fostering flexible career paths.”

I have a genuine passion for educating others and making a positive impact on young minds. This passion motivated me to overcome challenges associated with entering the teaching profession”.

“The decision of the non-educator graduates to become teachers by showing them a value to also share knowledge and expertise by teaching the students skills that are trending currently in demand in the society.”

2. Self-care and Professional Growth

Career growth or planning is a deliberate and ongoing process that individuals engage in to advance their careers and achieve personal and professional fulfillment. It involves setting goals, acquiring new skills, seeking out development opportunities, and making strategic decisions that align with one's aspiration. With this, self-care and professional growth is composed of factors such as professional support and mentorship and work-life balance.

Professional Support and Mentorship. Professional support and mentorship play crucial roles in the growth and development of individuals in various fields, including education. Professional support refers to the assistance, guidance, and resources provided to individuals to help them succeed in their careers. Mentorship, on the other hand, involves a more personalized and ongoing relationship where a more experienced individual provides guidance, advice, and support to a less experienced individual to help them navigate their career path. Here are the statements that support this idea;

“Mentors can offer insights into classroom dynamics, effective teaching strategies, and help navigate challenges unique to the teaching profession”.

“Peer Mentoring Programs: Pairing us non-education professionals with experienced educators who can provide guidance, support, and practical advice tailored to our specific context and challenges”.

“Find a mentor who is an experienced educator and can provide guidance, support, and advice tailored to the specific challenge”.

A mentorship program facilitates employees' smoother integration into the workforce, enhances their professional growth, equips them with the ability to implement values and strategies effectively, supplements ongoing formal education, training, and development endeavors, and opens avenues for career advancement.

Work-life Balance. It is the equilibrium between the time and energy dedicated to work and the time and energy allocated to personal life, including family, leisure, and other non-work activities. Achieving a healthy work-life balance is essential for individuals to maintain physical, mental, and emotional well-being while effectively managing their

professional responsibilities and personal commitments. Based on the informants, they said that;

“Balancing Work and Personal Life - proactively managing workloads to maintain a healthy work-life balance”.

“Prioritize self-care to maintain physical, emotional, and mental well-being amidst the demands of teaching”.

“Non-education graduates recognize the Importance of self-care and allocate time for personal interests, relaxation, and rejuvenation.”

Work-life balance encompasses two primary dimensions: engagement in both work and non-work life and minimizing conflict between social roles in these domains. This conceptualization leads to a review of evidence regarding the consequences of work-life balance on work-related, non-work-related, and stress-related outcomes. Antecedents to work-life balance, both personal and organizational, are identified, along with their effects. Theoretical mechanisms linking work-life balance to overall life satisfaction are described, followed by a discussion of future research directions and policy implications.

3. Financial Stability Considerations

These are crucial factors that individuals often consider when making decisions about their careers and livelihoods. Financial stability provides a sense of security and peace of mind, allowing individuals to meet their basic needs, plan, and pursue their goals and aspirations. It encompasses factors such as income, savings, investments, and access to resources and opportunities. The informants frankly stated that they were motivated to choose the teaching profession, despite not being educators by profession, due to considerations such as job stability, tenure security, and job opportunities.

“Individuals looking for a career with job security may find teaching to be a viable option.”

“Individuals seeking job stability and security may be attracted to teaching as a reliable second career.”

“Teaching also is a stable career choice with opportunities for job security, especially with tenure systems in place”.

“I am a hypocrite if I say that the stability is not appealing to me, as a non-education graduate, I am seeking a reliable career path for the future of my children”.

“It also offers opportunities for personal and professional fulfilment, making a positive impact, and long-term career stability.”

The positive impact of effective financial education training on teachers directly translates to higher levels of positive financial behavior in students. When teachers are equipped with the tools and knowledge to teach financial literacy effectively, students are more likely to develop sound financial habits and make informed decisions regarding their finances both now and in the future.

Pathways non-education graduates typically follow transitioning into a teaching career.

1. Career Shift

Career shift represents a transformative journey that allows individuals to pursue their passions, explore new interests, and unlock their full potential. While it may involve uncertainty and risk, the rewards of a successful career shift can be immensely gratifying, leading to greater satisfaction and fulfillment in both professional and personal life. Based on the informants' statement that shifting in another career has led to different reasons;

“Non-educators' graduates may choose to transition into teaching for various reasons”.

“It can drive individuals towards career change as personal fulfillment, fostering flexible career paths.”

Shifting careers is a dynamic process influenced by a multitude of factors, including generational differences, gender, immigration status, and socioeconomic background. These factors can significantly impact individuals' career decisions, aspirations, and opportunities for advancement.

2. Career Transition Programs

Career transition programs play a vital role in helping individuals navigate changes in their careers and successfully transition to new opportunities. By providing a comprehensive range of services and support, these programs empower individuals to take control of their career paths, overcome challenges, and achieve their professional goals.

The informants highlighted that institutions are offering specialized programs that enable them to qualify for the teaching profession.

“Many state colleges and universities offer special programs for those degree holders to acquire necessary qualifications or certification to become teachers offering a Diploma in Teaching course”.

“They commonly take a course Diploma in teaching and sometimes earn only 18 educational units for them to be able to take the Licensure Examination for Teachers”.

In addition, one informant stated that there should be special programs that cater to their professional needs.

“These programs should be designed to accommodate the specific needs and prior knowledge of non-education professionals and pair no-education to experienced mentors who can provide guidance, support, and practical advice throughout their transition period.”

Career transitions play a crucial role in fostering professional growth and achieving work-life balance in healthcare. These transitions offer opportunities for individuals to

advance their careers, pursue new interests, and find alignment between their personal and professional lives.

3. Streamlined Pathway for Certification

To a simplified and efficient process for individuals to obtain professional certification in a specific field or industry. This pathway is designed to reduce unnecessary barriers and streamline the certification process, making it more accessible and manageable for candidates. Accordingly, the informants emphasized that there were policies that support and certification programs;

“Policies that support alternative certification programs make it easier for non-education graduates to transition into teaching roles by providing streamlined pathways to obtain the necessary certifications”.

“Programs that offer alternative certification pathways are designed for individuals with non-education backgrounds, often streamlining the certification process, making it more accessible for non-education graduates to become certified teachers.”

“Teaching Certification Programs provide flexibility for individuals to earn teaching credentials through short coursework.”

Career pathways, which encompass industry-based certifications and internships, are essential for preparing young adults for the labor market. These pathways provide valuable opportunities for hands-on experience, skill development, and exposure to real-world work environments, ultimately helping individuals make informed career choices and transition successfully into the workforce.

4. Efficiency of Alternative Pathways

The efficiency of alternative pathways refers to their effectiveness in providing individuals with streamlined and accessible routes to achieving their goals, often bypassing traditional methods. These pathways offer alternatives to conventional educational or career routes, allowing individuals to pursue their aspirations in a more flexible and expedited manner.

“Non-education graduates may find these pathways appealing due to their efficiency, allowing them to enter the teaching profession more quickly compared to traditional routes.”

“Influencing perceptions of the profession, creating opportunities for alternative pathways to certification, and addressing factors such as salary, job security, and work-life balance”.

“Those pursuing flexible pathways enroll in teacher certification programs offered by universities or colleges.”

Alternative pathways like apprenticeships and non-graduate employment are discussed in focus groups and interviews. It explores how the transition to work and responsible adulthood, and the support received, varies widely among individuals not pursuing higher education, reflecting differences across families, communities, and employers Hogheim, S., & Federici, R. (2020).

Challenges and problems encountered by non-education graduates in a career shift into teaching profession.

1. Professional and Career Challenges

The transition from education to work is a critical phase in professional career development and competence. It highlights challenges faced by graduates in the early career stages, such as unemployment threats, inadequate skills, decreased self-efficacy, and increased stress. Additionally, it examines issues like professional identity instability, early attrition, newcomers' roles in work communities, and the significance of workplace learning. The chapter emphasizes the role of social partnerships in addressing these challenges from a professional competence perspective Thomson, M., & Palermo, C. (2018). The professional and Career challenges covered the following such as, the potential for burnout and credibility challenges.

Potential for Burnout. The risk of experiencing physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion because of prolonged stress and overwork, often in the context of one's professional responsibilities. Burnout can manifest in various ways, including feelings of fatigue, cynicism, and decreased efficacy in one's work.

The informants delivered opinions that in career transitions they undergo stress and burnout.

“Professional obligations and personal responsibilities can contribute to increased stress and burnout among non-educator graduates in teaching role”.

“Non-education graduates may experience increased stress and burnout if they lack adequate support systems or coping strategies”.

“Non-education graduates may underestimate the challenges associated with teaching, leading to burnout and job dissatisfaction if they are not adequately prepared for the demands of the profession.”

Some of the informants conveyed that while the teaching profession posed challenges, it was also characterized by its inherent complexity and the intricacies involved in its execution.

“Teaching can be emotionally demanding, requiring patience, empathy, and resilience to navigate challenges such as student behavior issues, academic pressure, and workload demands.

“These things contribute to the challenges encountered by non-education professionals by consuming all our time because of having many paperwork and other instructional materials to prepare that leading to stress that also affect to the family.”

Burnout often arises when discussing chronic stress experienced by individuals in professions involving frequent interaction with others, such as education. Teachers, who spend extensive time at work and engage in numerous relationships with students, colleagues, and parents, face mental and physical demands. Teaching and assessment

tasks further drain energy and effort. Consequently, the combination of resource demands, work requirements, and performance expectations can deplete teachers' energy and enthusiasm, potentially leading to burnout symptoms.

Credibility Challenges. It is the obstacles that individuals face in establishing trustworthiness and reliability in their professional roles or personal interactions. These challenges can arise due to various factors such as lack of experience, inconsistent behavior, or ethical lapses. Overcoming credibility challenges often requires demonstrating competence, honesty, and consistency in actions and communication. Additionally, building credibility may involve seeking feedback, admitting mistakes, and actively working to regain trust when it has been compromised. By addressing credibility challenges effectively, individuals can enhance their reputation and credibility, leading to stronger relationships and greater success in their endeavors.

The informants elaborated that lacking essential skills in teaching may result from several challenges.

“When non-education graduates enter the teaching profession, they may face several challenges such as lack of pedagogical knowledge, limited understanding of child development, difficulty in lesson planning, classroom management, limited knowledge of special education, & limited professional development opportunities.”

“Adapting to the dynamics of a classroom, managing student behavior, and fostering a positive learning environment can be challenging initially.”

“Credibility as educators, especially when lacking formal training or experience in the field of education, can pose significant challenges.”

The concept of credibility in the teaching profession can be understood in two dimensions: "credibility of the role" and "credibility in the role." The former refers to the overall prestige and social status attributed to the teaching profession and educational institutions within contemporary society. The latter refers to how individual teachers assume and enact their role, thereby making it credible or not credible in specific interactions, particularly within the classroom dynamic with students.

2. Lack of Support, Formal Training and Seminar

Drawing from the informants' statements, one significant factor contributing to these challenges was the absence of a support system. Given that they did not initially pursue education as their primary profession, they sought additional support such as training and seminars to address these needs.

“Non-education graduates may lack formal training in pedagogy, classroom management, and educational theory.”

“Non-education graduates lack training in pedagogy, and curriculum development. And classroom management techniques.”

They can affect their ability to effectively deliver the lessons, engage the students, and assess learning outcomes. As a result,

student achievement and overall learning experiences may compromise.”

The transition of educators from classroom to higher education settings, focusing on the support provided by a doctoral seminar called "Pedagogy of Teacher Education." Through collaborative self-study, the research sheds light on the development of identities as educators and future teacher educators within the course. Key themes identified include the cultivation of a collaborative mindset, the adoption of a teacher educator-researcher perspective, and the cultivation of critical self-awareness Bunn, G., & Wake, D. (2015).

Mental Health and Well-being Issue

It is an essential component of overall health, encompassing emotional, psychological, and social aspects of individuals' lives. It involves the ability to cope with stress, maintain positive relationships, and adapt to life's challenges effectively. Prioritizing mental health and well-being is crucial for promoting resilience, productivity, and overall quality of life. However, As articulated by the informants, their experiences underscore that teaching is a multi-tasking profession that often leads to exhaustion, which can significantly impact mental health and well-being.

“Teaching can be a demanding profession with long hours, high workload, and significant stress.”

“Having many paperwork and other instructional materials to prepare that leading to stress.”

“Requiring so much paper works and other non -teaching related works that make them exhausted”.

Mental health is foundational to the well-being and effective functioning of individuals, as emphasized by the World Health Organization. Teaching, being one of the most stressful professions, places significant importance on the mental health of teachers. The factors within educational institutions that contribute to mental health issues and lack of well-being among teachers. It highlights the importance of teachers' mental and physical health in fostering student and school well-being. By raising awareness of these factors, it aims to empower school authorities to address teachers' mental health concerns and promote well-being. Teachers, like all individuals, have their own needs and may benefit from motivational support from counselors. Ultimately, prioritizing mental health well-being among teachers can rejuvenate their energy, enhance professional growth, and foster the holistic development of students.

Non-education graduates cope with the challenges and problems encountered in transitioning into career shift.

1. Professional Growth and Development

Professional development is essential for teachers to continually enhance their skills, knowledge, and teaching practices. Through ongoing development opportunities, teachers deepen their content knowledge, refine their instructional strategies, and build collaborative networks. Professional growth not only benefits individual teachers but also

contributes to the overall improvement of education quality, Watters, J., & Diezmann, C. (2015).

Determination and Commitment. These are essential qualities for achieving success in any endeavor. In the context of education, determination refers to the firm resolve to overcome challenges and obstacles in pursuit of educational goals. It involves perseverance, resilience, and the willingness to persist even in the face of adversity. Commitment, on the other hand, encompasses dedication, loyalty, and a sense of responsibility towards one's educational objectives and responsibilities. The informants emphasized that to overcome challenges in the teaching profession, one should possess these qualities so that they are motivated to perform their work effectively.

“Despite potential challenges like limited networking opportunities, educators remain committed to their growth and the success of their students.”

“The determination of non-education graduates to overcome challenges contributes significantly to our overall success in transitioning to teaching. This determination serves as a strong motivator, driving us to give our best effort in our jobs and to persevere regardless of obstacles.”

“My commitment to ongoing growth and development enables me to evolve as effective educators and make meaningful contributions to student success.”

Self-determination theory posits that motivation exists on a continuum, ranging from intrinsic motivation, which arises from within oneself and is driven by personal satisfaction or enjoyment, to extrinsic motivation, which comes from external factors such as rewards or punishments. This theory emphasizes the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation and promoting well-being. Commitment towards their profession and their students directly influences the quality of education provided. Moreover, the impact of school leadership on teacher commitment is substantial. Effective school leaders who align their values with those of their teachers can positively influence teacher commitment, leading to better student outcomes.

Self-Efficacy and Confidence. are vital aspects of effective teaching practice. Educators who possess high levels of self-efficacy and confidence are better equipped to meet the challenges of teaching, foster student success, and contribute positively to the learning environment. As per the statements of the informants, recognizing accomplishments within the profession boosts confidence.

“Celebrating small victories helps build confidence and resilience in the face of challenges.”

“Determined individuals often embrace a growth mindset, believing that abilities.”

“Guidance that we find the most helpful in overcoming obstacles”.

Teacher self-efficacy influences instructional approaches, individual and collaborative endeavors, and persistence, and may fluctuate depending on the

circumstances and challenges encountered by teachers. And confidence plays a vital role in teachers' successful performance of professional activities, as it correlates positively with self-awareness and the desire for acknowledgment.

Attending Training and Seminars. It is a fundamental aspect of professional development for educators, providing opportunities to enhance their knowledge, skills, and instructional practices. These sessions offer valuable insights into emerging trends, teaching methodologies, and educational research, empowering teachers to stay updated with the latest advancements in their field. Additionally, training and seminars foster collaboration and networking among educators, facilitating the exchange of ideas and best practices. According to the informants, participating in such activities, teachers can improve their effectiveness in the classroom, contribute to student learning outcomes, and ultimately, advance their careers in education.

“Appropriate training and seminars are essential to prepare them mentally and emotionally for the teaching environment.”

“Giving proper and necessary trainings or seminars to enhance their skills and motivation to teaching.”

“Provide with opportunities to participate in training on seminars in relation to the personal development and self enhancement.”

“Workshops and training sessions specifically designed for non-education graduates that can help them develop essential teaching skills. These workshops can cover topics such as lesson planning, assessment strategies, differentiated instruction, and creating inclusive learning environments.”

Induction seminars for new teachers serve as crucial platforms for providing emotional support and creating a non-threatening environment. These seminars primarily focus on helping new teachers cope with discipline issues, bolstering their self-confidence, and fostering the development of a professional identity. By addressing these key areas, induction seminars aim to equip new teachers with the necessary skills and mindset to navigate the challenges of their profession effectively.

Skills Enhancement. The continuous development and improvement of educators' abilities to effectively fulfill their roles in the classroom. This process involves acquiring new knowledge, refining existing skills, and adapting teaching practices to meet the evolving needs of students and the educational landscape. The informants clearly emphasized that practical and hands-on training can enhance teaching skills.

“Offering practical and hands-on training experiences that allow non-education professionals to develop essential teaching skills in real-world classroom settings”.

“Non-education graduates who value intellectual growth and professional development may see teaching as a career that allows them to keep learning and adapting.”

“It recognizes the importance of specialized skills and understanding in catering to diverse learning requirements.”

Skill enhancement training refers to programs and initiatives designed to improve employees' skills and competencies in the workplace. These training sessions aim to bridge the gap between the skills demanded by industries and the skills acquired through academic education. By providing employees with opportunities to develop new skills or refine existing ones, organizations can positively impact employee performance and job satisfaction.

2. Collaboration and Partnership

The informants underscored the importance of receiving supervisory feedback and technical assistance from experts such as master teachers, principals, and supervisors. They highlighted that this support can significantly contribute to the development of their teaching skills.

“Supervisors can offer guidance and support based on the unique needs and experiences of non-education graduates”.

“Implementing regular check-ins with supervisors to discuss challenges, progress, and areas for improvement.”

“Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms - Establish constructive feedback and evaluation mechanisms to help non-education graduates reflect on their teaching practices.”

Teachers, collaboration provides opportunities for professional growth, sharing best practices, and gaining diverse perspectives that enrich their teaching practice. At the school level, collaboration fosters a culture of collective responsibility, promotes innovation, and leads to continuous improvement in teaching and learning. In addition, partnerships in teacher education play a crucial role in ensuring that teacher preparation programs are practice-relevant and effectively bridge the gap between theory and practice. Innovative thinking and competent academic leadership are essential in fostering these partnerships and maximizing their impact.

3. Adaptation and Flexibility

Educators who demonstrate adaptability can modify their teaching methods, curriculum, and instructional strategies to accommodate diverse learners and changing educational environments. Flexibility allows educators to embrace new technologies, pedagogical approaches, and curricular innovations, fostering a dynamic and responsive learning environment. Furthermore, informants provided insights into how successful non-educators exhibit adaptability and flexibility.

“In a way of successful non-education graduates demonstrate adaptability and flexibility in adjusting to the demand and dynamic of the teaching profession.”

“Flexible and adaptable in responding to the unique needs and challenges of students, colleagues, and the educational environment.”

Modeling resilience, adaptability, and lifelong learning is essential for navigating the challenges in education and inspiring others to embrace change and growth.

Effective teachers demonstrate the ability to adjust their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. However, the terminology used to describe this adaptive approach differs among academic disciplines, which can create barriers to effective communication and understanding among educators. Flexible learning is a guiding principle that empowers both learners and educators to make choices regarding the timing of their engagement, the resources they utilize, and their overall approach to education. This flexibility accommodates diverse learning styles and preferences, facilitating enhanced learning experiences across various modes of study.

4. Educational Access in Learning Resources

Teachers' access to learning resources directly impacts their ability to deliver high-quality instruction and support student learning outcomes. Providing teachers with the necessary tools, materials, and opportunities for professional development is essential for building a supportive and conducive learning environment. The informant highlighted that access to resources plays a crucial role in addressing various challenges encountered in the teaching profession.

“Addressing the challenges faced by non-education graduates transitioning into teaching careers requires a multi-faceted approach and access to various resources and support systems.”

“Access to Resources and Tools: Providing us with access to resources, tools, and technology that can support our teaching efforts, such as lesson planning templates, educational apps, and online learning platforms.”

K-12 teachers recognize the advantages of incorporating open educational resources (OER) into their teaching practices, acknowledging their potential to enhance student learning outcomes and provide diverse instructional materials (Tang, H. 2020.).

Conclusions

Non-education graduates are drawn to teaching careers by a variety of factors, including a focus on education and empowerment, a desire to make a difference, and the importance of self-care and professional growth. Financial stability considerations, such as job security and opportunities for personal fulfillment, also play a significant role. These diverse motivations reflect the multifaceted nature of their decision-making process.

Non-education graduates entering teaching careers have diverse pathways, including career shift opportunities and streamlined certification processes. These pathways prioritize job stability and professional development, offering tailored support to meet non-education professionals' needs. Their availability reflects the complexity of career transitions and underscores the importance of accessible routes into teaching.

Non-education graduates transitioning into teaching face several challenges. Burnout, exacerbated by stress and demanding roles, is compounded by insufficient support and training. Credibility issues stem from limited experience, impacting trustworthiness. Mental health concerns arise due to stress. Prioritizing mental health support is crucial for resilience and student outcomes. Collaboration between institutions and policymakers is necessary to address these challenges effectively.

Non-education graduates transitioning into teaching careers face challenges but also demonstrate qualities and strategies for success. Opportunities for professional growth, determination, and commitment drive educators to overcome obstacles. Self-efficacy and collaboration enhance effectiveness, while adaptability meets diverse student needs. Access to resources and integration of open educational resources enhance teaching effectiveness. Leveraging strengths, non-education graduates thrive in teaching, contributing meaningfully to education.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Educational institutions may recognize and address the diverse motivations that drive non-education graduates to pursue teaching careers. By understanding the significance of educational focus and empowerment, promoting self-care and professional growth opportunities, and providing financial stability, institutions can attract and retain talented individuals from various backgrounds. Fostering a supportive environment that values these motivations will not only enrich the teaching workforce but also contribute to the overall success and fulfillment of educators.
2. Non-education graduates embarking on teaching careers have diverse pathways to choose from. They may opt for career shifts driven by personal fulfillment and flexibility, engage in specialized training through career transition programs, utilize streamlined certification pathways, or explore alternative routes into teaching. Recognizing and supporting these pathways is crucial for empowering non-education graduates to successfully transition into teaching roles. By doing so, educational institutions and policymakers can enrich the teaching workforce and create a supportive environment for individuals eager to contribute to education.
3. Transitioning into teaching presents growth opportunities for non-education graduates despite initial challenges. They may face hurdles like burnout and credibility issues, yet institutions can support them through mentorship and professional development. Addressing the lack of support, training, and seminars enhances their classroom management and student engagement. Prioritizing mental health initiatives ensures they thrive in their roles. By fostering a positive

environment, educational institutions can facilitate non-education graduates' successful transition into teaching and enrich the field of education.

4. Non-education graduates transitioning into teaching face challenges, but with the right mindset and support, they can succeed. Recommendations include embracing professional growth through continuous learning, fostering collaboration with mentors and colleagues, adapting to changing educational needs, and ensuring access to learning resources. By being proactive and seeking support, non-education graduates can thrive in their new career path and positively impact their students' lives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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